

Thermal Decomposition and Kinetic Parameters of Chromium(III) and Thorium(IV) Complexes with Orthovanilin Oxime

M. L. DHAR*, ONKAR SINGH, NANI MAGAZINE and R. M. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 004

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The use of non-isothermal methods for finding the kinetic parameters (E , Z and ΔS^*) and the mechanism of decomposition of the complexes tris(orthovanilin-oximate)chromium(III) and tetrakis(orthovanilin-oximate)thorium(IV) is reported. The former complex decomposes regularly without any distinguishable rest in the curve while the latter decomposes with a distinguishable rest in the curve. Both the complexes involve random nucleation mechanism.

THE reported complexes¹ have been investigated for their mechanisms of decomposition and for their kinetic parameters using non-isothermal methods of decomposition.

Experimental

The complexes were thermogravimetrically analysed by a Paulik-Paulik MOM derivatograph² (Hungary) for obtaining DTG, DTA and TG curves. α -Alumina was used as the reference material.

Pilyan-Novikova³, Coats-Redfern⁴ and Horowitz-Metzger⁵ methods were employed for finding the kinetic parameters of complex $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3)_3]$ completely and for the first two steps of $[\text{Th}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. The graphs of Coats-Redfern, Horowitz-Metzger and α - $T(\text{K})$ were analysed for the mechanism of decomposition.

Results and Discussion

$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3)_3]$ complex starts decomposing at 463 K and this continues upto 1003 K. It decomposes regularly without any distinguishable rest in the curve, which corresponds to the loss of the ligand moiety. There is no further loss in weight beyond 1003 K when a stable oxide Cr_2O_3 as the end-product is formed.

$[\text{Th}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ complex starts decomposing at 371 K which continues upto 415 K when a rest in the curve is observed, which corresponds to the loss of one coordinated water molecule. The complex decomposes further at 453 K and continues upto 536 K, which also corresponds to the loss of the coordinated water molecule. The residual complex decomposes further upto 993 K with the loss of the ligand moiety. There is no further loss in weight as the stable oxide ThO_2 is formed.

The fractional weight loss (α) and the corresponding $(1-\alpha)^n$ were calculated from TG curves

(Figs. 1 and 2) at different temperatures, where n depends upon the reaction model. Pilyan-Novikova (Fig. 3), Coats-Redfern (Fig. 4) and Horowitz-Metzger (Fig. 5) graphs are found to be the best linear fits. Coats-Redfern, Horowitz-Metzger and α - $T(\text{K})$ (Fig. 6) analyses suggest random nucleation mechanism⁶. Kinetic parameter values and mechanism of decomposition are recorded in Table 1. The α - $T(\text{K})$ curves constructed on the basis of TG data for both the compounds are of the same pattern. The curves begin with an acceleratory period without any apparent induction period thus indicating that no surface nucleation or branching occurs before the start of these steps⁷.

Fig. 1. Simultaneous DTG-DTA-TG curves of $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3)_3]$ complex.

Fig. 2. Simultaneous DTG-DTA-TG curves of $[\text{Th}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{NO}_6)_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ complex.

Fig. 4. Coats-Redfern plots: (Δ) Cr^{III} complex and (\circ) 1st. step, (\odot) 2nd. step of Th^{IV} complex.

Fig. 3. Piloyan-Novikova plots: (Δ) Cr^{III} complex and (\circ) 1st. step, (\odot) 2nd. step of Th^{IV} complex.

Fig. 5. Horowitz-Metzger plots: (Δ) Cr^{III} complex and (\circ) 1st. step of Th^{IV} complex.

The values of slope, intercept and energy of activation were obtained from Figs. 3-5. The values of intercept and energy of activation (E) were

substituted in equation (1) for evaluating the values of Z in case of Piloyan-Novikova and Coats-Redfern, while the values of Z in case of Horowitz-Metzger were calculated by using equation (2). The

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Step	Equation	E kJ mol ⁻¹	Z s ⁻¹	ΔS* JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	Model*
[Cr(C ₈ H ₈ NO ₃) ₃]	1st.	Piloyan-Novikova	29.284 8	0.073 9	-119.394 0	—
[Th(C ₈ H ₈ NO ₃) ₄ .2H ₂ O]	1st.	Piloyan-Novikova	63.826 0	0.970 5 × 10 ⁶	-57 677 1	—
	2nd.	Piloyan-Novikova	60.634 7	0.305 4 × 10 ⁶	—	—
[Cr(C ₈ H ₈ NO ₃) ₃]	1st.	Coats-Redfern	36.380 8	0.290 3	-114.453 8	R.N.
[Th(C ₈ H ₈ NO ₃) ₄ .2H ₂ O]	1st.	Coats-Redfern	81.378 1	0.132 6 × 10 ⁶	-39.921 1	R.N.
	2nd.	Coats-Redfern	80.420 7	0.404 9 × 10 ⁶	—	R.N.
[Cr(C ₈ H ₈ NO ₃) ₃]	1st.	Horowitz-Metzger	50.624 4	1.568 5 × 10 ⁻³	-133.304 8	R.N.
[Th(C ₈ H ₈ NO ₃) ₄ .2H ₂ O]	1st.	Horowitz-Metzger	124.391 0	0.018 98	-107.297 0	R.N.

*R.N.= Random nucleation mechanism.

Fig. 6. $\ln(-T(K))$ plots: (Δ) CrIII complex and (\circ) 1st. step, (\circ) 2nd. step of ThIV complex.

entropy (ΔS^*) of activation was calculated by employing equation (3).

$$\text{Intercept} = \log \frac{ZR}{\beta E} \quad (1)$$

$$Z = \frac{E}{RT_m} \beta \exp \left(\frac{E}{RT_m} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$= \frac{kT_m}{h} \exp \left(\frac{\Delta S^*}{R} \right) \quad (3)$$

where, R represents the molar gas constant, β the rate of heating (Ks^{-1}), k the Boltzman constant, and h the Planck constant.

The study reveals that the complexes decompose with random nucleation mechanism. $[Cr(C_8H_8NO_3)_3]$ decomposes regularly in one step with the loss of the ligand moiety forming Cr_2O_3 as the end-product. $[Th(C_8H_8NO_3)_4 \cdot 2H_2O]$ undergoes dehydration in the first two steps, the third step involves the loss of the ligand moiety forming ThO_2 as the end-product.

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